

DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING COMPREHENSION COMPETENCE OF
ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE BASED ON
ANIMATION APPROACH.

**Kurbonova Mekhrangiz Khurshedovna,
Ochilova Maftuna Doniyor Qizi,
Murtazoyeva Muqaddas Sohob qizi.**

Teachers of English Faculty 2 ,
The Department of Integrated English Course ,
Samarkand State of Foreign Languages.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773708>

Abstract

The purpose of this article is a theoretical substantiation for the possibility of developing foreign language listening skills of elementary school pupils using animation .

Аннотация:

Целью данной статьи является теоретическое обоснование возможности развития навыков аудирования иностранного языка у учащихся начальной школы с помощью анимации.

Ключевые слова: Анимационные мультфильмы, Исследования в классе, Словары, ученики.

Keywords: Animation Cartoons, Classroom Action Research, Vocabulary, Young learner.

Introduction .

Despite the active use of video materials in the educational process in foreign languages, their diversity, the presence of a large number of video courses in foreign languages, the methodology for working with video materials has not yet been sufficiently developed. It is necessary to develop criteria for their selection, principles of classification, a methodology for working with them, including exercises and tasks for their effective use.

Features of the use of Animation in teaching foreign language listening in elementary school Scientists traditionally distinguish four types of speech activity: listening, speaking, writing and reading.

The formation of skills in all four types of speech activity is an important need of every modern person. However, according to research, the most commonly used type of speech activity is listening. Listening is characterized as a receptive type of oral speech. The importance of listening lies in the fact that without understanding the speech messages of the interlocutor, it is impossible to fully communicate orally.

From the point of view of the modern provisions of the methodology of teaching foreign languages, listening is “a receptive type of speech activity, in which simultaneous perception, comprehension and understanding of a speech message by ear is carried out, based on sensory experience (language, speech, practical life experience).

Listening is a complex receptive mental-nemic activity associated with the perception, understanding and active processing of information contained in an oral speech message. Listening is carried out as a result of performing a number of complex logical operations, such as analysis, synthesis, deduction, induction, comparison, abstraction, concretization, etc.

When characterizing the essence of perception (auditory and visual), it is necessary to strictly distinguish between two concepts: perception - the process of highlighting informative distinguishing features (i.e., the formation of images) and recognition - recognition of the formed image as a result of its comparison with the standard. Gez N.I. notes that the formation and recognition of images are of a phase nature, and although some authors have differences in the name and in determining the sequence of these phases, all works emphasize the close relationship between the processes of formation and recognition, etc perception and recognition.

Analyzing the features of identification, teachers point out that in most cases it does not have the character of an extended conscious action; if such an action is possible, it is observed only at the stage of image formation. As one gets acquainted with the material, the identification process changes, it is carried out instantly (simultaneously) with the help of the most necessary informative features. If these signs are not enough and the identification did not take place or turned out to be erroneous, then the perception again takes on more detailed forms and turns into a conscious perceptual action or into a series of sequential (successional) actions.

(Gez: 1981, 32) Simultaneous recognition prevails in the process of linguistic communication, although elements of succession are not excluded. The presence and expansion of the logical operations listed above depend, therefore, on the type of understanding: indirect (discursive) or direct. The latter is characterized, in particular, by the curtailment and abbreviation of mental operations carried out in inner speech.

Perceiving speech, the listener converts sound images into articulatory ones using a motor (speech-motor) analyzer.

A strong functional connection is established between the auditory and speech-motor analyzers. With regard to the visual analyzer, it is known that optical signals are superior to all others in obtaining information about the outside world. When listening, the visual analyzer greatly facilitates the perception and understanding of speech by ear. Such visual supports as speech organs, gestures, facial expressions, kinemas and others reinforce auditory sensations, facilitate internal pronunciation and understanding of the meaning of speech.

The significance of inner speech for understanding is very great.

Even in difficult conditions (meaning experiments with the use of internal noise), it makes it possible to perceive speech messages, predict and generalize.

At the initial stage of learning, inner speech proceeds especially intensively, and it can be considered as the main and necessary component of auditory perception.

At the advanced stage, there is a curtailment of motor activity, its reduction, which is explained by the strong unification of the speech-motor auditory and visual analyzers into a single system. This, in turn, affects the perception and understanding of speech.

The basis of the internal mechanism of listening are such psychological processes as listening, attention, recognition and mixing of language means, their identification, their comprehension, antipathy, grouping, generalization, affirmation in memory, inference, that is, the reconstruction of someone else's thought and an adequate reaction to it. . Therefore, the subject of listening is someone else's thought, encoded in the text and subject to recognition.

The product of this type of motor speech is a conclusion, the result is an understanding of the perceived semantic content and one's own response behavior, verbal and non-verbal.

So, the unit of this type of speech-motor is a semantic decision that determines the listener's further speech and non-speech behavior.

Distinguish contact and distant listening. In contact listening, it is indeed an integral part of oral interactive communication; in distant, mediated listening (for example, radio, television, phono recording, etc.), this form of communication is an independent form of speech communication with its own characteristics.

From the studies of domestic and foreign psychologists, it is known that the listener relies on listening to his alternative experience and sufficiently developed psychological mechanisms. Taking information of the phonological (lower) level, he must recode it into units of the conceptual (high) level, using various supports of perception, including the prompting function of situations. This process is strictly personal and complex, since it depends on many factors, including the

development of the student's speech hearing and memory, the ability to use probabilistic forecasting, and the presence of attention and interest.

In a number of foreign works devoted to the study of the so-called language ability (foreign language aptitude), speech hearing (intonation and phonemic) is one of the main conditions for successful foreign language learning (Correl W, Ingenkamp K.H., 1971). When perceived by ear, a phrase as one of the units of perception is understood not through analysis and subsequent synthesis of its constituent words, but as a result of recognition of informative features. Intonation is considered to be the most informative feature, since it has "perceived qualities", thanks to which the listener can segment speech into syntactic blocks, understand the connection between parts of the phrase, and, consequently, reveal the content.

When perceiving speech messages, first of all, the communicative plan of the statement is recognized, and intonation is one of the main structural features that distinguish communicative types of sentences: narration, question, exclamation, motivation. The logical and syntactic plans are distinguished with the help of logical stress and division of the phrase into syntagms. Emotional assessment, the desire to correlate any manifestation of feelings and will with objective reality are also expressed with the help of intonation, which contributes to understanding the subtext (V.A. Artemov, N.S. Fomenko, etc.). Performing these functions, intonational hearing simultaneously develops indicator signs (standards) that are necessary for the successful functioning of short-term memory.

If it is customary to understand intonation hearing as the ability to perceive the intonation structure of a phrase and correctly correlate it with the intonational variant, then phonemic hearing is understood as the ability to distinguish speech sounds and identify them with the corresponding phonemes. Phonemic hearing, as well as intonation, is necessary not only for the formation of adequate acoustic-articulatory images, but also for the use of patterns available in memory when recognizing new messages.

When perceiving foreign language speech, the listener must operate not only with a productive dictionary (the volume of which is very small for secondary school students), but also with a receptive one, acquired mainly in the process of reading. The visual image of a word imprinted in the memory is not always easy, as teaching experience shows, to be associated with auditory.

It is impossible not to mention, in addition, the so-called potential dictionary, which was not at all in the language experience of students (words of foreign

origin, compound or derivative words formed from affixes known to students, etc.).

The receptive and potential dictionaries are understood by the listener subjectively, depending on the topic, the conditions of perception, on the relationship between known and unknown vocabulary, i.e. from the ability to predict and use the instant choice of a solution from a number of probabilistic hypotheses.

The use of educational cinema can be considered as the highest form of situational visualization. The use of video materials in the process of teaching foreign languages can significantly increase the effectiveness of the teacher's teaching activities, since video materials are examples of authentic language communication, create an atmosphere of real language communication, make the process of mastering foreign language material more lively, interesting, problematic, convincing and emotional. Cinematography combines sounding speech with a dynamic image of life situations, allowing you to clearly identify the main signs of any situation.

It is known that the presentation of educational material using video is characterized by a number of specific features. These features include the following:

1) information is presented by means of art, which determines the presence of a figurative model for introducing material. The main characteristic of this model is the presence of a plot and composition. This fact emphasizes the proximity of the figurative model to art, on the one hand, and on the other hand, the difference between such a model and traditional means of teaching foreign languages; in this case, an emotional presentation of the educational material and its emotional perception are assumed. The use of video in the lesson contributes to the "effect of complicity and empathy with the characters", which in turn creates the conditions for real motivated communication in the classroom. Emotional motives in the activities of students are associated with the formation of an evaluative attitude;

2) information is presented dynamically, which enhances the effective aspect of learning, increases the density of communication in the classroom, and, consequently, increases the effectiveness of all learning activities. The dynamism and emotionality of the introduction of the material contribute to the memorization of information, increasing the likelihood of reproducing this content in the future;

3) information presented through video has a high degree of authority. The named credibility of video information is provided by the authenticity factor of the video materials used in the educational process, which gives rise to a high level of confidence in the perceived information on the part of the trainees. (Komarov: 2006, 188)

In order to most effectively use video in the process of teaching foreign languages, it is necessary to find out what are the advantages of the named teaching aid and its limitations in a number of other technical teaching aids.

Dave Willis highlights the following positive characteristics of using video in the learning process:

- the room does not require darkening, and, therefore, the contact of the teacher with the students is continuous;
- video provides the ability to use various modes of operation, for example, work with a freeze frame, work with a video track (when the audio track is turned off), etc.;
- video materials are easily used in various types of work: individual, pair, group, collective. (Willis: 1983, 17)

Margaret Allan adds one more positive quality to the above: video equipment allows you to divide the whole film into the required number of video fragments, depending on the goals, individual needs and characteristics of the trainees, and then work with each fragment separately. (Allan: 1983, 20)

It should be remembered that when planning work with video materials, it is necessary to have a clear idea not only of their functionality, but also of functional limitations, as well as to measure how the use of video materials is capable of realizing the specific goal of a particular lesson. Otherwise, there may be a danger of subordinating teaching activity to the logic of the functioning of video materials and "... TCO can turn into an expensive and sometimes simply unnecessary thing with an extremely low educational value." (Sosnovsky: 1991, 8).

Typology of video materials

In modern science, there are various typologies of video materials that offer to classify these video materials depending on certain factors. The most common typologies are:

- 1) for the purpose of creation - video materials specially created for educational purposes; non-educational video materials adapted for educational purposes; professionally filmed video materials commissioned by the educational institution; video materials independently filmed according to their own script;

- 2) by genre - video materials that are a feature film, video advertisements, cartoons, video clips, news blocks, fragments of talk shows, sports and historical chronicles, fragments of documentaries, etc.;
- 3) in terms of the number of topics covered - situationally single-topic and situationally multi-topic;
- 4) according to the method of production - filming, re-editing;
- 5) for didactic purpose - instructive, illustrative, instructive-illustrative;
- 6) in terms of structure and degree of completeness - integral and fragmentary;

7) according to the terms of use of video materials - materials for work under the guidance of a teacher and materials intended for independent work of students. (Bankevich L.V., Shelenger I.A., Ivanova-Tsyganova V.I., Platonova I.B., Pressman L.P., Shcherbakova I.A.)

In the process of teaching foreign languages, video materials can act in their various functional purposes. Depending on the setting, the duration of the presentation of the video material, the place of presentation of the video fragment in the system of work on the formation of foreign language skills and abilities, video materials can function as:

- meaningful support
- semantic support
- stimulus to speech

Methods of working with the film when teaching listening.

Working with a film fragment should be determined by the methodological task that is set before it - to serve as a means of developing listening skills.

Working with a movie fragment consists of the following steps:

1. Work with unfamiliar words.

You should not work with students on those unfamiliar words and phrases that can be understood by them from a situational context, and do not affect the understanding of the storyline of the film fragment. On the one hand, this develops students' linguistic conjecture, and on the other hand, it helps to overcome the fear of meeting unfamiliar words in a clear context. Work on new words should be carried out on an oral basis or on the basis of oral anticipation, 2-3 lessons before the film is shown, and it should not take more than 3-4 minutes

2. Introductory conversation.

Before the demonstration begins, the teacher should check if the students understand the title of the movie correctly. It is very important that the teacher

informs that there may be words that are unknown to the students. The teacher should advise them to try to guess the meaning of unfamiliar words and understand the statements.

3. Viewing a movie clip.

From the very beginning, the film fragment must be shown to the class at least 2 times. If the teacher sees that many students did not understand a significant part of the film fragment, the fragment should be shown with the sound turned off, so that the teacher himself commented on it, but always in English, and then show the fragment again.

4. Checking the understanding of the movie clip.

The main task facing the teacher at this stage is to check the students' understanding of the content of the fragment. The following workflows can be recommended here:

- a) teacher-student dialogue. Questions can be put in the following order: general, disjunctive, alternative, special. Thus, the plot of the film is reviewed 3-4 times;
- b) students determine whether this or that statement of the teacher corresponds to the plot of the film;
- c) the teacher's retelling of the content of the film fragment, in which phrases would come across that do not correspond to the plot of the film. Students who notice such phrases should raise their hand, after which the teacher himself can give the correct answer.

So, we have shown the sequence of work on the film fragment. When viewing a sound bite, listening acts as a learning goal.

As practice shows, video materials can be most effectively used in teaching oral foreign language speech. Let us consider what is the sequence of stages of working with video materials, as well as what is the content of these stages, if the task of methodological activity is the formation of oral utterance skills.

Video-based learning involves five stages of work:

- 1) preparatory
- 2) receptive
- 3) analytical
- 4) reproductive
- 5) productive

Conclusion

It should be emphasized the importance of using films and videos in the educational process when teaching listening to sounding speech. This is due to the following reasons. Firstly, because screen media for modern children are

common and favorite, and meeting them in English lessons gives them joy. Secondly, the very use of this tool helps the teacher to reveal his creative abilities. Thirdly, the use of screen tools helps the teacher to expand the range of situations within the topic being worked out, each time introducing something new that arouses interest among students and gives them an impetus for expression and, therefore, allows for a more complete implementation of the communicative orientation of the learning process.

The use of video materials in the process of teaching foreign languages can significantly increase the effectiveness of the teacher's teaching activities, since video materials are examples of authentic language communication, create an atmosphere of real language communication, make the process of mastering foreign language material more lively, interesting, problematic, convincing and emotional.

REFERENCES:

1. Барменкова О.В. Видеозанятия в системе обучения иностранной речи. //ИЯШ. – 1999, № 3. – С. 20-25.
2. Беляев Б.В. Очерки по психологии обучения иностранным языкам. – М., 1965.
3. Бим И.Л. О преподавании иностранного языка на современном этапе // ИЯШ, №3, 1995.
4. Бориско Н.Ф. Сам себе методист. - Киев: Фирма «ИНКОС», 2001. – С. 151-178.
5. Браун Дж. Восприятие английской речи на слух. – М., 1984
6. Вайсбурд М.Л. Обучение учащихся средней школы пониманию иностранной речи на слух. – М., 1965.
7. Ваулина Ю.В. Английский язык для студентов дошкольного воспитания. – М., 1994.
8. Гальскова Н.Д. Современная методика обучения иностранным языкам, - М., 2000.
9. Гальскова Н.Д., Гез Н.И. Теория обучения иностранным языкам: Лингводидактика и методика: Учеб. пособие для студ. лингв. ун-тов и фак. ин. яз. высш. пед. учеб. заведений. – М.: Издательский центр «Академия», 2004. – С. 161-189.
10. Allan M. Teaching English with Video // Video-applications in ELT. - Pergamon Press, 1983.
11. Anderson A. and Lynch A. Listening. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1988.
12. Field J. Skills and strategies: towards a new methodology for listening. ELT Journal, 1995, 52/2; 110-118.

13. Harmer Jeremy. How to teach English. – Longman, Pearson Education Ltd., 1998. – P. 97-110.
14. O'Malley J., Chamot A. and Kupper L. Listening comprehension strategies in second language acquisition. Applied Linguistics 10/4, p. 418-437. 1989.
15. Scrivener Jim. Learning Teaching. A Book for English Language Teachers. - Oxf., Macmillan Publishers Ltd., 2005. – P. 170-183.
16. Willis D. The potentials and Limitations of Video // Video-applications in ELT. - Pergamon Press, 1983.

